

Job Design And Employee Motivation Of Vegetable Oil Firms In Anambra State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study analyzed the job design and employee motivation of vegetable oil firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. The objective of the study was to determine the effect of job description on employee motivation of vegetable oil firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. Evaluate the effect of skill variety on employee motivation of vegetable oil firms in Anambra, State, Nigeria. Two research hypotheses were formulated in line with the objectives of the study. Descriptive survey design method was used; the sample techniques employed simple random sampling. The population for this research work is 432 respondents. The researcher distributes four hundred and thirty-two (432) questionnaires but only four hundred and nine (409) copies of questionnaire were retrieved. Correlation and t-test were used to test the hypothesis. The finding of the study shows that Job description has significant positive effect on employee motivation of vegetable oil firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. Skill variety has significant positive effect on employee motivation of vegetable oil firms in Anambra, State, Nigeria. The study recommends vegetable oil firms can create jobs that are challenging, rewarding, and aligned with employee motivations, ultimately leading to increased job satisfaction, productivity, and employee retention

Keywords: job design, employee motivation, vegetable oil, job description, and skill variety

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The surge in globalization and industrialization has precipitated an unparalleled proliferation of diverse organizations dedicated to addressing various needs. At the heart of these organizations lies the pivotal element of their workforce-the employees Hussein, (2020). In the dynamic landscape of contemporary business, characterized by constant technological evolution, a diverse workforce, varying age demographics, globalization, and evolving job designs, there is a critical focus on examining how these factors influence employee performance (Guidice, Heames & Wang, 2019).

In the knowledge economy era, the key to thriving workplaces lies in the adept utilization and cultivation of employees' skills. This encompasses not only technical proficiency but also the implementation of robust job design mechanisms that directly impact both employee productivity and overall organizational performance. Acknowledging that human resource utilization stands as the cornerstone and most pivotal responsibility in any organization, it becomes imperative for management to grasp the intricacies of each employee's role within the organizational framework (Amakiri & Godday, 2016).

Job design is the most important function of Human Resource Management. It indicates that, designing of contents, methods, functions of a job. Job design is the process of Work arrangement (or rearrangement) aimed at reducing or overcoming job dissatisfaction and employee alienation arising from repetitive and mechanistic tasks. Through job design, organizations try to raise productivity levels by offering non-monetary rewards such as greater

satisfaction from a sense of personal achievement in meeting the increased challenge and responsibility of one's work. Job enlargement, job enrichment, job rotation, and job simplification are the various techniques used in a job design exercise (Ghazi, 2016).

1.2. Statement of the Problem

The scourging problems that bedevil many organizations in Nigeria, including low employee and organizational performance cum productivity, inefficiency, poor/lack of technical-know-how, negative workplace politics, etc. are traceable to lack of/low staff training. This is very worrisome. Job design influences employee performance in several ways, positively or negatively, depending on how the job is designed. The job design of both private and public organizations influences their employees' performance and organizational productivity likewise. Employee's talents and insight can design productivity, improvement and innovation. Job design can ensure that skills are effectively used as well developed in the workplace.

In spite of the immense benefits, potentials and prospects of jobs design, only a very few organizations/institutions in Nigeria practice or give attention to it, thus making it a wasted resource in the struggle to improve competitiveness and employee well-being. Many workplaces (organizations) are characterized by a waste of employees' talents. Job design should be considered a high priority issue for managers and policy-makers alike. This also applies to staff training in Nigeria, especially in public organizations/institutions, whereby staffs are mostly poorly trained and retrained all because of workplace politics and being economical to avoid spending on training the staff.

In sum, the gross negligence, inappropriate, ineffective and misplacement of job and poor staff training by most organizations in Nigeria constitute some academic and managerial worries (problems) that deserve a work of this kind. This study rises to this challenge, with a view to proffering scholarly solutions to these rising inherent problems associated with job design and staff training, which adversely affect employee performance in organizations.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective is to critically examine the job design and employee motivation of vegetable oil firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to:

- i. Determine the effect of job description on employee motivation of vegetable oil firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.
- ii. Evaluate the effect of skill variety on employee motivation of vegetable oil firms in Anambra, State, Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.0 Conceptual Review

2.1 Job Design

Oldham and Hackman (2010) explain that job design is the content of any job so that the job holder's varied requirements are adequately met. Daniel et al. (2017) emphasized that job design combines various jobs, duties, and responsibilities to produce a composite that individuals may use in their work and view as their own. It is critical since it is required to complete the job efficiently, inexpensively, reliably, and

safely. Cummings and Worley (2014) indicate that job design intervention causes workers to notice and recognize meaningful changes over time. Henderson and Sowa (2022) posit that job designs that provide high levels of staff control also create favourable conditions for workers' training and development. Job design has also been defined as "the process to optimize organizational goals of efficiency and productivity and how workers can be satisfied doing it, optimizing individual goals of personal growth and wellbeing (Nmdu 2013). Job design is defined as "the content, methods and relationships of jobs in order to satisfy work requirements for productivity, efficiency and quality, meet the personal needs of the job holder and thus increase levels of employee engagement (Armstrong 2019).

2.2 Employee Motivation

Motivation can be defined broadly as the direction and persistence of an activity. Motivation is a feature that keeps employees attached to their jobs, and hence, their interests lead to originality and creativity (Rasheed *et al.*, 2020). Motivational theories aim to create a healthy work environment to ensure employees meet management's expectations. The ideas explain why employees behave in specific ways (Renata *et al.*, 2018). Motivation theories discuss how a company may persuade people to use their skills, efforts, and abilities to meet their needs and fulfill the company's objectives. This concerns the aspects that contribute to job satisfaction and organizational performance. Motivating employees is about getting them to move in a way that will help the firm achieve its stated goals and improve organizational performance (Huang *et al.*, 2019; Loh, 2019; Paais & Pattiruhu, 2020; Quadri, 2019; Soraya & Pedo, 2021; Sweis *et al.*, 2019).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on the job characteristics theory. The job characteristics theory as propounded by Hackman and Oldham (1976) suggested that a well-developed job design can cause the employee to be more internally motivated, satisfied with their overall job and personal growth opportunities, generate higher quality working life and have lower absenteeism and/or turnover rates. This, in turn, will result in positive work outcomes. The theory was originally intended as a way to evaluate jobs and to see if they should be redesigned to increase employee motivation and productivity. The job characteristics theory has three primary components: core job dimensions, critical psychological states, and work outcomes.

However, this theory is essential to this study in the sense that it enables the manufacturing firms to know the features of the job in terms of the skills required, task identified, the meaningfulness of the job, the responsibility for the outcome of the job etc. This serves as a driving force that makes the employees give out their best in their job because they are valued and treated as tangible assets. Also, it enables employees to know what is expected of them in the process of carrying out their tasks and duties which will boost their morale thereby improving performance. Perhaps the earliest attempt to design jobs came during the era of scientific management. Scientific management as propounded by Taylor (1911) proposed a number of ideas that have been influential in job design. An important idea was to minimize waste by identifying the most efficient method to perform the job. Using time-motion studies, management could determine how much time each task would require and plan the tasks so that the job could be performed as efficiently as possible.

2.3 Empirical Studies

Ogbu, Agbaeze and Emeali, (2024) examined the effect of job design on employee performance in Benue State Civil Service, Makurdi. The specific objectives were, to: determine the effect of task variety on employee productivity in Benue State Civil Service; investigate the extent to which job autonomy affect employee engagement in Benue State Civil Service; and evaluate the extent to which feedback mechanism affect job satisfaction in Benue State Civil Service. The study adopted a survey research design with a total population of 657. Census sampling technique was used, which meant that the entire population was used. However, a total number of 650 duly completed and returned copies of the questionnaire were used for data analyses. The study adopted stratified sampling technique to reach out to the different ministries selected. Regression analysis was used for data analysis at 5% level of

significance. Findings revealed that job design had a significant positive effect on employee performance in Benue State Civil Service, Makurdi.

Ntadom, Atueyi & Jacobs (2021) examined the effect of career development on organizational performance, a Study of selected higher institution in Anambra State Nigeria. The study was anchored on Self-concept theory of career development. As a cross-sectional survey the research design were used, a structured questionnaire instrument were developed and used for data collection by the researcher to which reflect such options as strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree, which is popularly referred as five (5) points likert scale. It was used to obtain information from the respondents. The population of the study comprised of 57, 710 students selected across the five south east states of Nigeria. A sample size of 399 students was drawn from the population, using Taro Yamane formula of which three hundred and forty-seven (347) copies of questionnaires were duly completed and returned; showing 96% response rate. Research hypotheses were tested using ANOVA regression analysis which was carried out with the aid of Statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 23. The study found that career development has significant effect on Organizational Performance.

Ezeamama, (2019) investigated the relationship between job satisfaction and employee productivity in Anambra State University. The study was a survey research design based on a sample of 312 staff of the population of then on-teaching staff of the Anambra State University. The cross sectional survey was conducted between January, 8 2013 and February 11, 2013. A questionnaire was developed on which the respondents indicated their level of agreement based on five-point Likert scales ranging from 1 (“strongly disagree”) to 5 (“strongly agree”). Cronbach’s alpha (α) analysis (0.75 for job satisfaction and 0.84 for productivity) test the internal consistency of the variables obtained in the sample showed that the instrument is reliable. Descriptive statistics: Mean standard, frequencies and percentages were used to analyse the demographic characteristics and answer the research questions, while the Friedman’s Chi-square test was used on hypotheses one and two while Spearman’s ranked correlation analysis was adopted to test the hypotheses three. The SPSS version 17 for windows (a computer based statistical programme) was used to run all the analyses for the study. The results showed that the employees of Anambra State University are significantly satisfied from the job they do and are significantly productive. Further results indicated that there is very weak positive but insignificant relationship between job satisfaction and employee productivity in Anambra State University. The study thus concluded that job satisfaction is not a contributor to the employee productivity in the public sector of Nigeria, as the Institutions do not cue their plans towards satisfying the needs of the employees

Ohene, et al. (2024) explored the impact of job design and employee involvement on Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs’) performance. Data was collected from 367 employees of Ghanaian SMEs using random sampling. IBM SPSS 24 and AMOS-SEM were used for confirmatory factor analysis and to analyze the latent variables. The measurement model was tested on the entire dataset using exploratory factor analysis. The investigation demonstrated a strong fit for a four-factor hypothesis model. The study revealed a statistically significant beneficial relationship between job design and employee involvement in organizational performance. It also found a favourable correlation between job design, employee involvement and motivation. However, there was a negative correlation between employee motivation and organizational performance. The study uniquely focused on SMEs in an emerging economy like Ghana using financial sector tiers two and three. The implication is that job design and employee involvement improve SMEs’ performance and give them a competitive advantage.

Amodu, Okeke and Nwangwu (2023) examined the job redesign and employee productivity in Vegetable oil firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. The study adopted survey method of research. Data were generated through primary and secondary sources. The method for data collection was questionnaire which was administered randomly among the staff of the selected vegetable oil firm. The population of the study was 942; the sample size of the study was the same population because it is not up to 1000. While eight hundred and seventy-three (873) were retrieved. The hypotheses were tested using regression analysis method at 0.05% level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that, Job enrichment has a significant and positive effect on employee commitment of vegetable oil firms; Job enlargement has a

significant and positive effect on employee commitment of vegetable oil firms; Job autonomy has a significant and positive effect on employee commitment of vegetable oil firms.

Manafa, Okeke & Atueyi (2022) analyzed the strategic thinking and performance of Foam Industry in Anambra State. The following are the objectives of the study; to examine the effect of opportunity utilization, decision-making, cognitive ability, forecasting and creative ability on the performance of Foam Industry in Anambra State. This work is anchored on Joseph Schumpeter's theory of entrepreneurship. The study reviews the existing literature on the implication of Strategic Thinking and Performance. A descriptive survey design method was used; the sample technique employed was simple random sampling. ANOVA method of data analysis was used. The population of the study is 1393 where the sample size of 304 using Taro Yamane Formula. The researcher administered 304 questionnaires but only 302 were retrieved and used for the analysis. Structured questionnaires were used to gather information from the population. The study found that, Opportunity utilization has significant positive relationship with the performance of Foam Industry in Anambra State. Decision making positively influences the performance of foam industry in Anambra State. Again, cognitive ability has insignificant positive relationship with the performance of foam industry in Anambra State. Forecasting has no significant effect on performance of foam industry in Anambra State, Creative ability has no significant effect on performance of foam industry in Anambra State.

METHODOLOGY

Research design is simply the blue print which researcher used in carrying out research work and for the purpose of this study, the survey research design were used to build the impact on job satisfaction and employee productivity. The data used for this research work were obtained specifically from two sources namely Primary and Secondary sources. The population for the study comprised the staff of the six (6) Vegetable oil firms in Anambra state, Nigeria. Such as VINO pure vegetable Oil, Star Arrival Vegetable Oil, Sonwatex Sunny Vegetable Oil, Baron Vegetable Oil, Promac Vegetable Oil, Envoy Oil Industry, which give a total of 432 staff. The researcher make use of questionnaire structured into two sections. This was designed in such a way to obtain relevant information from the respondents. The first section looked at the personal data of the respondents while the second section concern the respondents' perception on the investigation of job design and motivation of Vegetable oil firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. Hypotheses were tested, using correlation and t-test. The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Analysis were carried out with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and Regression Analysis.

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

4.1 Distributions of Questionnaire

Table 4.1.1 Information on Distribution of Questionnaire

s/n	Options	No of Respondents	Percentage %
1	Questionnaire Distributed	432	100%
2	Questionnaire Returned	429	99%
3	Questionnaire Completed	409	94%
4	Questionnaire Not Duly Completed	12	3%
5	Questionnaire Missing	8	2%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4.1 showed that a total number of four hundred and thirty-two (432) copies of questionnaire were distributed to the respondents, four hundred and twenty-nine (429) copies which represented 99% were returned, four hundred and nine (409) which represent 94% where completed and twelve (12) copies which represented 3% were not duly completed by the respondents, while eight (8) copies which

represented only 2% of the total questionnaire were missing. Hence, the analyses for this study were based on the four hundred and nine (409) copies which represented 94% of the sample population.

4.2 Test Of Statement Of Hypotheses

HO₁: Job description has no significant positive effect on employee motivation of vegetable oil firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

HO₂: Skill variety has no significant positive effect on employee motivation of vegetable oil firms in Anambra, State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis one

HO₁: Job description has no significant positive effect on employee motivation of vegetable oil firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Correlations

		EPM	JOD		
Spearman's rho	EPM	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.974**	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	
		N	409	409	
	Bootstrap ^b	Bias	Std. Error	.000	.000
			BCa 95% Confidence Interval	Lower	.943
		Upper	.996		
		JOD	Correlation Coefficient	.974**	1.000
			Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
	Bootstrap ^b	Bias	Std. Error	.000	.000
			BCa 95% Confidence Interval	Lower	.943
Upper		.996			

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

b. Unless otherwise noted, bootstrap results are based on 409 bootstrap samples

Paired Samples Test

		Paired Differences				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower				Upper
Pair 1	EPM - JOD	.66259	.55888	.02763	.60827	.71692	23.977	408	.000

Table 1a indicates the relationship between the independent variable Job description and the dependent variable employee motivation. At a 0.05 level of significant, 95% confidence level interval ranges between .996 and .716 at the upper case, and also 943 and 608 at the lower case, with a 2 tailed test of sample distribution showing the critical area in a distribution. The spearman correlation coefficient shows a value of 97% which shows a high correlation coefficient between the dependent and independent variable. This further portrays the high goodness of fit of the model

Model 1= $EPM = \beta_0 + \beta_1 JOD + \mu$

Table 1 indicates the difference in mean value (.66259) and standard deviation (.55888) for the extent of relationship that existed between the variables included in the group. The single group variables in model one of the hypotheses are represented by EPM & JOD (employee motivation & job description).

However, the paired sample t-test showed that employee motivation level increased significantly when job description practice is adhere to. A t-test value of job description is said to be significantly high when it is above 2 or equal to 2 (t-value > 2), but when the t-value is less than 2 (t-value < 2), it is concluded that the perceived outcome within the paired sample has no significant relationship. In conclusion to this result, the t-value was obtained at 23.977 which is significantly high. The study therefore concluded that there is a significantly positive relationship between job description and employee motivation of vegetable oil firms in Anambra, State, Nigeria

Decision Rule: Accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than 0.05, otherwise, reject.

Decision: We reject the null hypothesis, since the p-value is 0.000** which is less than the critical value 0.05, this study reveals that Job description has significant positive effect on employee motivation of vegetable oil firms in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

HO₂: Skill variety has no significant positive effect on employee motivation of vegetable oil firms in Anambra, State, Nigeria.

Correlations

		EPM	SKV		
Spearman's rho	EPM	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.797**	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	
	N	409	409		
	Bootstrap ^b	Bias	.000	.000	
		Std. Error	.000	.025	
		BCa 95% Confidence Interval	Lower	.	.746
			Upper	.	.847
	SKV	Correlation Coefficient	.797**	1.000	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	
		N	409	409	
Bootstrap ^b		Bias	.000	.000	
		Std. Error	.025	.000	
		BCa 95% Confidence Interval	Lower	.746	.
			Upper	.847	.

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

b. Unless otherwise noted, bootstrap results are based on 409 bootstrap samples

Paired Samples Test									
		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	EPM - SKV	.21271	.97329	.04813	.11811	.30732	4.420	408	.000

Table 2 indicates the relationship between the independent variable Skill variety (SKV) and the dependent variable employee motivation (EPM). At a 0.05 level of significant, 95% confidence level interval ranging between 0.847 and 0.307 at the upper case, and also 0.746 and 0.118 at the lower case, with a 2 tailed test of sample distribution showing the critical area in a distribution. The spearman correlation coefficient shows a value of 0.79%, which shows a high correlation coefficient between the dependent and independent variable. This further portrays the high goodness of fit of the model

Model 2= $EMP = \beta_0 + \beta_1SKV + \mu$

Table 2 indicates the difference in mean value (.21271) and standard deviation (.97329) for the extent of relationship that existed between the variables included in the group. The single group variables in model two of the hypotheses are represented by SKV & EMP (Skill variety and employee motivation). However, the paired sample t-test showed that employee motivation level increased significantly when the perceived Skill variety was adopted. A t-test value of Skill variety is said to be significantly high when it is above or equal 2 (t-value > 2.00), but when the t-value is less than 2.00 (t-value < 2.00), it is concluded that the variable within the paired sample has no significant relationship. In conclusion to this result, the t-value was obtained at 4.420 which is significant high. The study therefore concluded that there is a significantly high positive relationship between Skill variety and employee motivation of vegetable oil in Anambra State

Decision Rule: Accept the null hypothesis if the p-value is greater than 0.05, otherwise, reject.
Decision: We reject the null hypothesis, since the p-value is 0.000** which is less than the critical value 0.05, this study reveals that Skill variety has significant positive effect on employee motivation of vegetable oil firms in Anambra, State, Nigeria

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion, job design plays a crucial role in driving employee motivation in vegetable oil firms in Anambra State. By designing jobs that are challenging, meaningful, and rewarding, vegetable oil firms can boost employee engagement, productivity, and job satisfaction. However, designing effective jobs requires an understanding of employee needs and preferences, as well as the ability to balance employee autonomy, feedback, and rewards with organizational goals and objectives. By investing in job design, vegetable oil firms in Anambra State can build a motivated and productive workforce that drives business success and long-term growth. Effective job design involves a thorough understanding of the skills, interests, and goals of employees, as well as the organizational objectives and resources. By balancing these factors, vegetable oil firms can create jobs that are challenging, rewarding, and aligned with employee motivations, ultimately leading to increased job satisfaction, productivity, and employee retention.

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